

TOWARD A PEDAGOGICALLY-INFORMED FRAMEWORK DERIVED FROM CHOMSKY'S TRANSFORMATIONAL GRAMMAR THEORY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18244985>

ABSTRACT

Syntax is essential for sentence generation as it determines word order and structure. Transformational Grammar (TG), a key development in 20th-century linguistics, emerged from efforts to explain how speakers articulate thoughts in their language, stemming from the cognitive revolution of the 1950s. This study investigated the whys and hows of improving the pedagogical aspects of Transformational Grammar Theory, focusing on its development and practical applications in the "Structure of English" course. Through thematic analysis of interviews, two main themes emerged: (1) Factors leading to the Pedagogical Improvement of the Theory, and (2) Practical Application to Teaching Innovations. Under the first emerging theme, one of the findings revealed the theory's limited scope to fully master syntax. Moreover, despite the incompleteness, TG's concepts are a good source for teachers' pedagogical initiatives, and while there are concept complexities, these are manageable for linguistics students. On the other hand, the second theme articulated the inclusion of additional grammatical topics, utilization of a bottom-up structured teaching strategy, and the application of TG's competence-performance distinction to assessment. A conceptual framework was proposed to demonstrate pedagogical improvements to the theory's relevance in modern language teaching, especially in Syntax.

Keywords: *Chomsky's Transformational Grammar Theory, Syntax, Pedagogy-oriented Theory Improvement*

INTRODUCTION

Syntax plays a crucial role in generating sentences as it governs the structure and order of words within a sentence. According to Topping (1970), the description of grammar at the level of structures arose as a result of the objective of transformative grammar to describe the speaker's ability to express himself in his own language.

Transformational grammar is a specific theory within generative grammar that dates back to the 1950s, the period when the cognitive revolution began (Sogutlu, 2022). The most significant development in linguistic theory and research in the 20th century was the rise of generative grammar, and, more especially, of transformational-generative grammar, or transformational grammar, as it came to be known.

This theory explains a phenomenon. In particular, it is a descriptivist theoretical perspective in response to traditional grammar, namely prescriptivism (Gbolagade, 2021). In other words, it describes and analyzes actual language use rather than prescribing (Williams, 2005). It describes two main types of rules: the rules of phrase structure, which govern the structure of a sentence as consisting of a noun phrase and a verb phrase, and the transformational rules, which transform sentences from affirmative to interrogative or from active to passive (Sogutlu, 2022).

Two versions of transformational grammar were put forward in the mid-1950s: the first by Zellig S. Harris and the second by his pupil, Noam Chomsky. It was Chomsky's system that attracted the most attention. As first presented by Chomsky in *Syntactic Structures* (1957), transformational grammar can be seen as both a reaction against post-Bloomfieldian structuralism and a continuation of it.

Generative-transformational grammar studies linguistic competence in order to describe the user's ability to create an infinite number of sentences. Unlike traditional grammars, which analyze sentences by words, transformative grammar analyzes them by phrases. Each sentence has its own syntactic components, which belong to specific categories within a hierarchical connection.

Chomsky is generally associated with cognitivism, innatist theory, generative grammar, and universal grammar theories. These all indicate that children acquire language innately and naturally (Alqahtani, 2022). Chomsky believes that language competence is partly innate and that our children are born with a language acquisition device (LAD), or language competence, which equips them for language learning. LAD is supposed to consist of three elements: a hypothesis-maker, a linguistic universal, and an evaluation procedure (Xia, 2014).

The general tenet of TGG holds that every language speaker has relatively few simple sentence patterns, called kernels, and a complex set of rules that combine to form more complex sentences (Hayes, 1967). That describes the operations in which a language speaker combines and modifies simple sentences into a finite set of rules to produce more complex sentences.

The process is technically referred to as “Transformations”. In other words, a speaker learns a finite set of basic sentence patterns together with a finite set of transformational rules. So, following these rules, he may construct an infinite number of sentences. Hence, we have the Phrase Structure Rule of Grammar as the first tenet of TGG. The second is the Transformational Structure Rule, which posits that five transformational rules operate in reality (Thomas & Kintgen, 1974).

Thus, the words this boy, this girl are treated as noun phrases (NP), very nice and quite nice as adjective phrases (AdjP), and in class, with parents, from work as prepositional phrases (PP). Consequently, the words that came out of the class with her parents are treated as dependent on the verb phrase (VP). The way the phrase is structured is done with the corresponding symbols for each word of the sentence.

The two basic concepts of transformative grammar are deep structure (DS), which provides a detailed reflection of syntactic structure, and surface structure (SS), which provides a more concise and less detailed overview (O'halla, 2001). Johnson (2004) identified these concepts in his exploration of TG: Phrase Structures, Positioning Arguments, Verb Movement, Determiner Phrases and Noun Movement, Complement Structure, Subject and Complex Predicates.

Moreover, the concept of transformational generative grammar arises from the belief that sentences as a unit of grammatical analysis possess transformational capabilities; these capabilities are made possible by one dominant feature of grammar which is ‘recursiveness’, that is, the expansion of the kernel sentences to produce many more rule-governed sentences that are plausible and correct by all standards (Chomsky, 1957).

The kernel sentence has not undergone any transformation (i.e., processes such as negation, passivization, or interrogation have not been applied to it). The kernel sentence is often in the ‘SP’ format as in ‘girls sing’, ‘dogs bark’, birds chirp, goats bleat, boys sweat, etc., from the examples stated above, many other varieties can be generated such that the above sentences can be re-produced in an SPA, SPAA, SPAAA format, and many more.

For example:

- I. Boys sweat profusely (SPA)
- II. Goats bleat incessantly in the morning (SPAA)
- III. Birds chirp sonorously in the jungle whenever they are feeding.
- IV. Bees buzz in the morning, sometimes at noon, but mostly at night. (SPAAA)

Unlike traditional grammars, which analyze sentences by words, transformative grammar analyzes them by phrases. Each sentence has its own syntactic components, which belong to specific categories within a hierarchical connection (Radford, 1988; Broderick, 1975). Broderick (1975) even argues that this kind of grammar, which does not accumulate but generates constituent structures, is also called a generative theory.

Regarding criticisms of the theory, Transformational Grammar offers much to the teaching of grammar, but it has limitations (McCormick, 1972). While its explicitness is a virtue of

transformational grammar, it also limits the scope of grammar by concentrating on "generating sentences." In addition, the work of the transformational grammarians is not complete; their system does not yet encompass a major description of English as a whole. Indeed, all linguistic approaches have shortcomings of one type or another.

Moreover, TGG is recondite and inaccessible to a layman (Orimogunje, 2021). TGG has failed in both comprehension and pedagogical practicability. Many critics leveled a slur at TGG's obscurity as a theory. That is to say, TGG does not seem to really meet the standard of simplicity that a theory of language should wield. His idea of grammar is too psychological and mathematical to merit a deserved explanation of language, according to many critics. Thus, he recounted that Transformational Grammar is pedagogically incongruent to the needs of a secondary curriculum. The theory is aimed at linguists, psychologists, and mathematicians rather than English teachers. Likewise, since TGG is esoteric and abstract, it does not easily satisfy pedagogical purposes.

According to Djeribai (2016), little research has been conducted on the implications of Chomsky's theories for language teaching and learning. Opong (2019) further rearticulated that transformational generative "is not concerned with English teaching methodology... no teaching procedures of transformational grammar that can be converted into teaching procedures, but it gives implicit assumptions about language teaching to be dealt with to derive some teaching English methodology".

In light of the compelling theoretical arguments and criticisms, this paper sought to address the need to investigate why and how to pedagogically improve the Transformational Grammar Theory in teaching the course "Structure of English". Finally, to provide an illustrative output, this paper proposed a conceptual framework for the improved theory.

Research Questions

This paper aimed to answer the following specific research questions:

1. What are the identified grounds for pedagogically improving the TGG Theory in teaching "Structures of English" course?
2. How can the TGG Theory be pedagogically improved in teaching "Structures of English" course?

METHODOLOGY

Since the goal of this research was to enhance the TGG theory, the researcher employed the formative research method. According to Reigeluth (2009), formative research is a developmental or design-based research aimed at improving a specific case or an existing design theory. This method is particularly suitable for the study, as it seeks to refine the TGG theory, a linguistic theory, into an instructional theory applicable to real-

world instructional practice. Specifically, it focuses on adapting the theory for use in the "Structure of English" course within the BSEd-English program.

Formative research follows a case study approach. In doing a designed case to improve a theory, the following are conducted: 1) Select a design theory; 2) Design an instance of the theory; 3) Collect and analyze descriptive and formative data on the instance; 4) Revise the instance; 5) Repeat the data collection and revision cycle; and 6) Offer tentative revisions for the theory.

A case study, on the other hand, could gain a deep understanding of the research design inherent in the data (Zaidah, 2007). This is focused on a limited number of participants due to the need for a thorough examination of individuals, topics, and issues (Armfield, 2007). The case study design entails six steps: defining the research question (often starting with "how" or "why"), selecting the case and specifying data collection methods, preparing for data collection, gathering and organizing field data, conducting data analysis, and ultimately reporting the findings (Schoch, 2020).

The key informants in this paper were eight college students, purposively selected from one of the state universities in Bohol. These informants were carefully selected based on their enrolled program and the course they were taking. They are all Bachelor of Secondary Education students majoring in English in their first year, enrolled in the course "Structures of English". Their level of proficiency in the course is varied to avoid bias from selecting only outstanding performers. Furthermore, the fundamental criterion for their selection was the course in which the students are enrolled, ensuring its suitability for discussing syntax, where the transformational grammar theory is incorporated.

In this study, the researcher served as the primary instrument for data collection. The data were obtained through in-depth, one-on-one interviews. An interview guide was developed to ensure that the questions were aligned with the study's area of inquiry.

In the pre-data-gathering phase, the researcher prepared the necessary research instruments and consent forms for the in-depth interviews. This phase also involved selecting key informants. After they provided consent to participate in the study, the researcher discussed the study's purpose, the time required to complete the interview, and plans for using the interview results. After all these concerns were addressed, the researcher conducted the in-depth interview with the key informants.

After the data were gathered, the researcher employed Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase thematic analysis method: (1) familiarization with the data, (2) generating initial codes, (3) searching for themes, (4) reviewing themes, (5) defining and naming themes, and (6) producing the report. This structured process enabled systematic identification and interpretation of patterns in the data, thereby supporting the study's analytical clarity and theoretical grounding.

Coding constituted a critical process for connecting data collection with theoretical analysis by systematically identifying patterns and recurring themes within verbatim

interview transcripts. Drawing on established qualitative methodologies (Harrison et al., 2017; Chun et al., 2019), key concepts were coded, refined, and synthesized while preserving their original meaning. This structured approach enhanced the study's credibility and rigor, consistent with the interpretive principles (Yazan, 2015).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of transcripts revealed two major themes that describe the underpinnings of the Transformational Grammar Theory and its significance to English language teaching, as seen through the key informants' perspectives. Each theme was labeled with a phrase derived from the formulated meanings of the informants' responses. The two major themes and their sub-themes, as derived from the present set of transcripts, were as follows:

Table 1. Emergent Theme 1: Factors Leading to the Pedagogical Improvement of the Theory

INITIAL CODES	CODED MEANING	SUB-THEMES
Incompleteness of phrase structure and transformation rules alone in mastering Syntax	The theory's core rules (phrase structure and transformation rules) do not fully encompass the knowledge needed to understand English syntax. Students recognize the need for supplementary concepts such as grammatical categories and functions.	Limited Comprehensiveness of the Theory
Despite its incompleteness, TG's concepts are a good source as a teaching guide.	TG serves as a helpful foundation for educators in understanding and explaining internal sentence structures. Teachers find value in using the theory to inform and guide their instructional strategies.	Call for Pedagogical Initiatives
Complex yet manageable concepts, especially for the linguistically-inclined students	While TG contains complex ideas that may initially seem difficult, learners, especially those with a background in linguistics, can eventually understand them. The concepts are not entirely inaccessible and can be taught effectively with appropriate strategies.	Manageable Complexities of Concepts for Linguistics Students

Sub-theme 1: Limited Comprehensiveness of the Theory

In the discussion of the theory's limitations, this theme reveals that the theory's basic concepts do not fully capture students' knowledge of, or mastery of, English syntax. It can be inferred from the idea that the phrase-structure rules and transformational rules entail knowledge of other relevant syntactic concepts. Moreover, learning syntax may require

including other relevant aspects, such as grammatical categories and functions. This is evident in the following respondents' statements:

R.B.: "There are still the parts of speech, those grammatical categories..."

R.A.: "It's not complete, it still needs the others—there are even grammatical functions."

This result deviates from TG's concept of linguistic analysis based on phrases (Broderick, 1975). This means that the theory requires the practice of traditional grammar, in which analysis begins with the words. This suggests that, in certain instances, a more granular analysis starting at the word level may be necessary or preferred to a solely phrase-based approach.

Moreover, this sub-theme aligns with McCormick's (1972) criticism that the work of the transformational grammarians is incomplete and has shortcomings; their system does not yet encompass a comprehensive description of English as a whole. By acknowledging the incompleteness of transformational grammar in providing a holistic description of English, there is a need to adopt a more eclectic approach, drawing on multiple theoretical perspectives to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of language structure and usage, including traditional grammar and structural grammar.

Sub-Theme 2: Call for Pedagogical Initiatives

This theme underscores the usefulness of the theory in teaching English syntax. It implies that the theory's concepts state acceptable facts on what is actually happening to the internal structures of English. On the positive side, it indicates that the teachers need to be knowledgeable about its concepts, and creative in teaching approaches. This is evident in the statements:

R.G. – "This can help as a guide in teaching, so that I can explain better and be effective for my student."

R.C. – "...Able to think of approaches in teaching and educational methods."

This addresses Orimogunje's (2021) criticism that TG does not serve pedagogical purposes efficiently. The perspective here is that Chomsky provided teachers with a blueprint for what to teach, while empowering them to determine how to deliver the teaching.

This sub-theme underscores the relationship between theory and practice in education. While theory provides a foundation, educators must adapt and apply these principles in the classroom. Moreover, it emphasizes the importance of teacher autonomy and innovation in crafting effective learning experiences tailored to students' needs.

This also speaks to the ongoing dialogue within the educational sector about the role of theory in pedagogy. It suggests that theories such as the Transformational-Generative theory can serve as valuable tools for guiding teaching practices. However, their effectiveness ultimately depends on how educators interpret and implement them in real-world educational contexts.

Sub-theme 3: Manageable Complex Concepts for Linguistics Students

Exploring the concepts of TG, it was found that some aspects of the theory are difficult to understand. Moreover, this is from the perspective of college students specializing in English doing linguistic analyses. For them,

R.F. – “From my perspective, sir, the disadvantage of Chomsky's theory is that it can be quite complex. Since his theory is extensive, it can be challenging to understand, particularly for those unfamiliar with linguistics.”

R.E. – “For me, sir, the disadvantage is that for slow learners, it is not easy to understand because it's too complex and the theory is very broad. Also, there are others who have difficulty comprehending it because of how broad it really is.”

R.C. – “It's complicated to understand and identify, sir, but once you analyze the sentence, you eventually get it.”

R.D. – “It's not that difficult, sir; it's still manageable...”

Regarding the criticisms, Orimogunje (2021) stated that TG is recondite and inaccessible to laypeople. However, in this paper, the students who can be considered linguists can manage the complexities of its concepts. This implies that while TG may pose challenges, it is not insurmountable, especially for individuals with a focused academic interest in linguistics.

Moreover, this may imply that these manageable concepts will be retained as part of improving the theory. The enhancement of the theory does not mean changing such high-level, rigorously conceptualized ideas, but instead filtering for comprehensible, empirical concepts to include and apply in the course “Structures of English”. In this way, the aspects of the theory that are more readily grasped and supported by empirical evidence serve as entry points for students, without compromising the preservation of the core theoretical foundations.

Table 2. Emergent Theme 2: Practical Application to Teaching Innovations

INITIAL CODES	CODED MEANING	SUB-THEMES
Inclusion of additional topics	There is a need to expand the subject matter beyond phrase structure and transformational rules by incorporating essential syntactic topics. By adding these complementary concepts, instruction becomes more complete and effective.	Enrichment of the Subject Matter
Specific-to-general topic arrangement	Teaching strategies should follow a bottom-up, topic-level sequence, with foundational knowledge (e.g., parts of speech, grammatical functions) taught before more complex structures (e.g., phrase-structure rules). This ensures logical progression and effectively scaffolds student learning.	Bottom-Up Structured Teaching Strategy

Application of TG's competence-performance distinction	Assessment practices should incorporate Chomsky's concept of linguistic competence and performance. Competence can be assessed through analysis tasks (e.g., identifying parts of speech, diagramming), while performance can be assessed through application tasks (e.g., writing, sentence construction).	Integration to Assessment
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Sub-theme 1: Enrichment of the subject matter

This sub-theme means that relevant topics will be incorporated into teaching English Structure, beyond the rules initially included in the theory. This is evident in the following statements:

- R.D. – “Those topics you included in our class, sir.”
- R.C. – “In fact, it's already more than enough, sir.”
- R.A. – “Those are essential topics that should be included.”
- R.G. – “Yes, sir, that's it (topics included in the syllabus). No need to add more...”

This will address the first sub-theme of the mentioned factor to improve the theory. This fills the gap in understanding phrase-structure rules and transformation rules alone. Simply put, these concepts will be added to relevant concepts to fully assess proficiency in syntax. These topics include: lexical and grammatical categories; phrases and their types; clauses and their types; sentences; grammatical functions; sentence patterns; syntactic structures; and processes.

To support this point, Ohalla (2001) noted that the grammatical functions of categories, such as the subject, predicate, or object, should not be confused with the labelling of categories, such as noun phrase, verb phrase, noun, verb, etc.

Sub-theme 2: Bottom-up Structured Teaching Strategies

This theme means applying “Prerequisites” at the topic level or using the “specific to general” teaching strategy. Usually, prerequisites are intended at the course level rather than at the topic level. A prerequisite is anything an individual needs to know or understand before learning something new. It includes a skill set that must be demonstrated before tackling a new, related concept that requires foundational knowledge.

The following statements are evidence of this theme:

- R.H. – “There is a need to arrange the topics from specific to general.”
- R.B. – “Phrase structure rules cannot be learned if the parts of speech are not taught first.”
- R.E. – “There should be a background on grammatical functions so that sentence patterns can be better understood.”

This implies that the topics in the previously mentioned sub-theme should be arranged so that knowledge of a concept is required for a new, more complex concept. This way, the organization of topics follows a logical progression, with each new concept building on previously acquired knowledge. This sequential arrangement ensures that students can effectively comprehend and engage with increasingly complex ideas by first establishing a solid foundation. By structuring the curriculum in this manner, educators facilitate a smooth and coherent learning experience, allowing students to scaffold their learning and achieve deeper comprehension as they progress through the course.

Sub-theme 3: Integration to Assessment

As for the teaching innovation in terms of assessment, the TG theory's distinction between linguistic competence and performance is applied. The statements depict how varied assessment methods can be utilized to measure both competence and performance:

R.C. – “When it comes to competence, it’s about analyzing things like what part of speech a word is, the type of phrase, and other related details....”

R.D. – “Linguistic performance could either be sentence construction or actual writing.”

R.A. – “Tree diagramming tests the linguistic competence.”

R.F. – “Example is what kind of verb is used, or what is the grammatical function of the words.”

Assessment has been and can never be detached from language teaching. Chomsky's distinction between linguistic competence and performance is made clear through its integration into assessment. By integrating this distinction into assessment practices, educators can design evaluations that not only measure students' language proficiency but also provide insights into their underlying linguistic competence.

For instance, assessments may include tasks that require students to demonstrate their understanding of grammatical structures, sentence formation, or syntactic transformations, thus assessing their linguistic competence. Additionally, performance-based assessments, such as oral presentations or written compositions, allow educators to evaluate students' ability to apply their linguistic knowledge in communicative contexts, assessing both competence and performance.

Conclusions

The improvement of Transformational Grammar (TG) Theory for instructional use in the course “Structure of English” is driven by both theoretical and pedagogical considerations. While TG offers a solid foundation for analyzing sentence structure, its limited scope, focused primarily on phrase structure and transformation rules, falls short of providing a comprehensive understanding of English syntax. This gap underscores the need to integrate grammatical categories and syntactic functions to enhance learning outcomes.

Despite its complexity, TG remains a valuable resource, especially when taught with accessible strategies tailored to linguistically inclined students.

To bridge theory and practice, this study proposes practical innovations in teaching. Enriching the subject matter by including supplementary syntactic topics and adopting a bottom-up, structured teaching sequence ensures that foundational knowledge supports the acquisition of more abstract linguistic concepts. Moreover, applying Chomsky's competence-performance distinction in assessment practices provides a balanced approach to evaluating both theoretical understanding and practical language use. Together, these insights support the development of a more comprehensive, accessible, and pedagogically sound framework for using TG in the classroom.

Recommendations

Since the second theme and its sub-themes clearly depict the changes leading to the pedagogical improvement of Transformational Grammar Theory, the conceptual framework presented on the next page, as an illustrative output, is proposed to outline how a student could be guided in mastering English syntax. Moreover, this will be a valuable guide for teachers teaching grammar at the syntactic level.

To better understand the framework, arrows pointing to a box indicate that the box is a prerequisite. For example, knowledge of syntactic structure requires knowledge of the concepts under phrases, clauses, and sentences. Apparently, sentences require knowledge of clauses, which in turn require knowledge of phrases, and phrases require foundational knowledge of lexical or grammatical categories.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Improved Theory

On the other hand, the phrase-structure rules are retained at the level of the “phrases” topic. In contrast, transformation rules are retained below the “syntactic rules and processes” topic, and all belong to the sentential level. Notably, with the arrows indicating different meanings, linguistic competence and linguistic performance both point to the syntax topics, implying that the overall ideal proficiency of a student should encompass all the included sub-topics.

Finally, the researcher also proposed a blended name, ExTra, meaning “in addition” and standing for “Extended Transformational,” a pedagogically improved Grammar Theory by Chomsky that adds and combines concepts to aid teachers in teaching grammar. Moreover, this name does not just imply transformational rules in syntax but also transformational learning in syntax. This pedagogically improved syntactic underpinning is expected to have a meaningful impact on students' grammar learning and mastery.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In accordance with ethical research standards, informed consent was clearly communicated to and obtained from all participants before each interview. To ensure anonymity, pseudonyms were assigned, and all identifying information in the interview transcripts was altered or removed. Field notes containing pseudonyms were securely

stored in a separate location, and confidentiality was rigorously maintained throughout the research process. Additionally, to protect both participants and the institution, the report intentionally omitted the institution's name, thereby preserving the privacy of all parties.

Acknowledgments

The researcher expresses his profound acknowledgment to Dr. Socorro Anne R. Zaluaga, his professor in the Theory Development course, and to Dr. Jean Roy, Dean of the College of Education, for their support and encouragement in publishing this research. Sincere appreciation is also extended to the panel of evaluators for their valuable insights during the research colloquium, which greatly enriched the quality of this paper.

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